

more active. In comparison to the triazino derivatives, the corresponding hydrazinomethyl derivatives were found to be more active.

Experimental

M.ps. were determined in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. The structures were supported by elemental analysis tlc, uv (EtOH), ir (KBr), nmr (TFA) and mass spectral data.

General procedure. 1,4-Benzoxazin-3(2H)-one (1a) : A mixture of *o*-halophenol (0.1 mol), chloroacetamide (0.1 mol) and anhydrous K_2CO_3 (4.2 g) in ethanol (50 ml) was refluxed for 3 h in an oil-bath. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol, (70%), m.p. 170°.

4-Carboethoxymethyl-1,4-benzoxazin-3(2H)-one(2a) : A mixture of 1a (0.05 mol), bromoethylacetate (0.05 mol) and anhydrous K_2CO_3 (3.0 g) in methanol (25 ml) was refluxed for 4 h. The solvent was then removed under reduced pressure and the separated solid crystallised from ethanol to yield 2a (74.4%), m.p. 90; $C_{12}H_{13}O_4N$; λ_{max} (EtOH) 282 nm; ν_{max} 1750 (C=O ester) and 1700 cm^{-1} (C=O δ -lactum); δ 1.4 (3H, t, CH_3 ester), 4.50 (2H, NCH₂CO), 4.3 (2H, q, CH_2 ester) and 6.7–7.1 (3H, m, ArH).

4-Hydrazinomethyl-1,4-benzoxazin-3(2H)-one (3a) : A mixture of 2a (0.018 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (80%; 0.026 mol) in ethanol (10 ml) was refluxed for 15 min. On cooling, white needle shaped crystals were separated to yield 3a (80%), m.p. 165°, $C_{10}H_{11}O_3N_2$; λ_{max} (EtOH) 292 nm; ν_{max} 3300 cm^{-1} (NHNH₂); δ 2.5 (2H, br s, NH₂) and 8.2 (1H, br s, CONH exchangeable with D₂O).

2(H),4(H)-8,10-Dibromo-1,2,4-triazino [3,4-c]-1,4-benzoxazin-5-ones (4a) : A mixture of 3b (0.001 mol), ammonium acetate (0.01 mol) in glacial acetic acid (5 ml) was refluxed for 5 h. The resulting dark brown solution was cooled, poured into crushed ice and neutralised with ammonia. The solid that separated was filtered and crystallised from ethanol to yield 4a (65%), m.p. 146°; $C_{10}H_7O_2N_3Br_2$; ν_{max} 3400–3200 (NH) and 1650 cm^{-1} (C=N); δ 4.15 (2H, s, NCH₂CO), 5.2 (2H, s, OCH₂), 7.8 (1H, br s, CONH exchangeable with D₂O).

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Phenolic Constituents from Leaves of *Rhus semialata* Murr.

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THE genus *Rhus* (Anacardiaceae) consists of several species of trees shrubs and climbers. A number of chemotaxonomically significant biflavones have been isolated from *R. succedanea*¹, *R. toxicodendron*², *R. punjabensis*³ and *R. mysurensis*⁴. Bagchi *et al.*⁵ isolated only agathisflavone from the leaves of *R. semialata*. The present paper deals with the isolation and characterisation of ethyl gallate, agathisflavone, robustaflavone, amentoflavone and myricetin from the leaves of *R. semialata*. The occurrence of myricetin is the characteristic feature of the genus *Rhus*.

Leaves of *R. semialata* were collected from Royal Botanical Garden, Godawari, Lalitpur, Nepal. The dried and crushed leaves (0.5 kg) were extracted first with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) and then with acetone. The acetone extract was concentrated under reduced pressure. It gave positive colour test with Mg/HCl (orange). The crude mixture (3 g) was chromatographed on a column of silica gel (8 g); eluted with benzene, ethyl acetate, ethyl acetate–acetone (8 : 2) and then with ethyl acetate–methanol (9 : 1). RS-I was isolated from the ethyl acetate eluate. The fraction eluted with ethyl acetate–acetone (8 : 2) was found to be a mixture of biflavones (RS-II and RS-III), which were further separated by preparative tlc (benzene–pyridine–formic acid, 36 : 9 : 5). The ethyl acetate–methanol (9 : 1) eluate gave RS-IV.

RS-I was crystallised from EtOAc–acetone as yellowish solid, m.p. 155°; appeared brown in uv light and gave blue colour with alcoholic $FeCl_3$, R_f 0.50 (BPF), $C_9H_{10}O_5$ (M^+m/e 198); m/e 198 (85, M^+), 183 (15), 170 (20), 153 (100, $C_7H_8O_4$), 125 (50), 113 (10), 108 (5), 107 (15), 79 (60), 53 (25), 39 (55) and 27 (45), δ (DMSO- d_6) 1.32 (3H, t, J 7 Hz, CH_3), 4.24 (2H, q, J 7 Hz, CH_2) and 7.11 (2H, s, H-2,6). From these data and by direct comparison with an authentic sample it was found to be ethyl gallate.

The ethyl acetate–acetone fraction was further separated by preparative tlc (benzene–pyridine–formic acid, 36 : 9 : 5) as RS-II ($R_f=0.15$) and RS-III ($R_f=0.18$).

RS-II was comparable with agathisflavone⁶ but after methylation it was found to be a mixture of agathisflavone hexamethyl ether⁷ and robustaflavone hexamethyl ether⁷ on comparison with authentic samples (m.p., R_f , fluorescence in uv light).

RS-III on methylation gave amentoflavone hexamethyl ether⁹ (m.p., R_f , shade in uv light).

RS-IV was crystallised from methanol as yellow needles, m.p. 358–59°, $R_f=0.12$ (BPF, 36 : 9 : 5), brown colour in uv light and green colour with alcoholic FeCl_3 . The uv spectra with diagnostic reagents⁹ showed free hydroxyls at positions 3, 5, 7, 3', 4' and 5', respectively. On acetylation with acetic anhydride and pyridine it gave the hexaacetate, m.p. 218–19°; δ (CDCl_3) 6.86 (1H, d, J 2.5 Hz, H-6), 7.33 (1H, d, J 2.5 Hz, H-8), 7.61 (2H, s, H-2', 6'), 2.31 (12H, s, OAc-7, 3', 4', 5') and 2.42 (6H, s, OAc-3, 5). From the spectral data and by direct comparison, it was found to be identical with 3,5,7,3',4',5'-hexahydroxyflavone (myricetin).

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Crystalline Constituents of *Flueggea microcarpa* Blume

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FLUEGGEA *microcarpa* Blume¹ (Syn. *F. virosa* Roxb., Fam: Euphorbiaceae) is an important medicinal plant found throughout India upto 5000 ft

altitude and in deciduous forests. It has important medicinal property, and the leaves, made into paste with tobacco, is used to kill worms in sores. The roots are used to treat and cure gonorrhea. Earlier workers² reported the presence of alkaloids and the foaming qualities of the plant. Work was done on the pharmacological action of the plant but the extracts were not carefully studied for their crystalline constituents. Hence, a comprehensive and systematic investigation was carried out and the findings are presented herein.

The aerial parts of the plant was powdered and extracted successively with hexane, chloroform and methanol. The hexane extract, after removal of waxes, was chromatographed over silica gel using benzene as the eluent. Three compounds A, B and C were secured. Compound-A was recrystallised from methanol and was identified as β -sitosterol. Compound-B was recrystallised twice from chloroform-methanol as shining needles, m.p. 276°; $[\alpha]_D^{25} +5^\circ$ (c 1.0 CHCl_3); M^+ 426 (31%); m/e 411 (20%), 302 (100%), 287 (57%), 204 (97%), 189 (23%), 135 (53%), 121 (40%) and 109 (34%). It was identified as taraxerol by a direct comparison with an authentic sample (m.m.p. and co-tl).

Compound-C was recrystallised from methanol as colourless needles, m.p. 180–2° (Found (C, 80.50; H, 11.63, $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{52}\text{O}_2$ requires: C, 80.38; H, 11.71%); $[\alpha]_D^{25} +42^\circ$ (c 1.0 CHCl_3); δ CDCl_3 ; (TMS) 0.85–1.0 (9H), 1.05–1.15 (9H) and 1.5–1.8 (6H); total 24H ($-\text{CH}_2$); δ 3.3–3.1 (br, OH), no peaks in the down-field region; M^+ 444 (9%); with $\text{Py}-\text{Ac}_2\text{O}$, it formed an acetate (crystallised from alcohol), m.p. 169–71° (Found: C, 78.59; H, 11.06, $\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{54}\text{O}_3$ requires: C, 79.01; H, 11.11%); $[\alpha]_D^{25} +54^\circ$ (c 1.0 CHCl_3); δ 0.85–1.0 (9H, $3 \times \text{CH}_3$), 1.05–1.15 (9H, $3 \times$ methyls); 1.5–1.8 (6H, gem-dimethyl adjacent to an oxygen function-supposed to be a bridged oxygen), 2.1 (3H, acetate protons). Compound-C underwent facile oxidation to give a ketone and dehydration with POCl_3 . The above data suggest that it may be a new saturated tetracyclic triterpene with a 3β -OH and an ether bridge in the side chain. The mass spectral data suggest that the ether bridge may be at $\text{C}_{24}-\text{C}_{25}$ position. Further studies to fix the position of the ether bridge, based on chemical and spectral data, confirmed the saturated triterpene structure as 3β -OH, 24–25 ether of lanostane.

The chloroform extract after concentration and crystallisation from CHCl_3 -MeOH failed to give solid, hence it was chromatographed over silica gel using benzene as eluent when two compounds D and E were obtained. From m.p., ir and other spectral data, compound D was identified as lupeol³, m.p. 212°; $[\alpha]_D^{25} +25^\circ$; the acetate, 221°; $[\alpha]_D^{25} +41^\circ$ (c 1.0 CHCl_3). Its identity as lupeol was